

<p>1. Be invited to a usability study</p> <p>Join our research! Scan the QR code for more information</p>	<p>2. Ask questions</p> <p>I can help you with those! You can ask as many questions as you need.</p>	<p>3. Make an informed choice about taking part</p> <p>Why me? Is this research for me? What will I be asked to do? Will I be comfortable taking part and who do I talk to? What are the benefits and drawbacks of taking part?</p>
<p>4. Establish the process for compensation</p> <p>Keep your travel receipts so we can reimburse you. We also need to know which voucher you'd like as payment for your time.</p> <p>Thanks. Will there be lunch?</p>	<p>5. Work out the practicalities</p> <p>What date? Where am I going? What time? Who am I meeting?</p>	<p>6. Give informed consent</p> <p>I know how the research data and my personal data will be collected, stored and used. I know how to access this data. It's okay to withdraw from the study at any time. I'm ready to sign the consent form.</p>
<p>7. Discuss access needs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Will I need specialist equipment? <input type="checkbox"/> Is there a lift? <input type="checkbox"/> I need to change the time. <input type="checkbox"/> I need a screen reader. <input type="checkbox"/> I am bringing someone to support me. 	<p>8. Complete the usability study tasks</p> <p>Remember, ask questions and you can withdraw at any time. We will observe you doing the tasks.</p> <p>Usability tasks</p>	<p>9. Review the research findings</p> <p>The researchers told me how to find the results. I'm going to look and I might give feedback.</p> <p>Results</p>